

Clinical and microbiological characteristics of literature patients (n = 57).

Reference	Gender	Age	Comorbidities	Species	Sequencing	Type of infection	Medication	Surgery	Outcome
Playe et al, ^[49]	Male	63	Asthma	<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i>	No	Brain abscesses and pachymeningitis	TMP-SMX, imipenem, and amikacin*	No	NA
Raby et al, ^[50]	Male	81	Diabetic mellitus, polymyalgia rheumatica, and gastric adenocarcinoma	<i>Nocardia mexicana</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscesses	Ceftriaxone and linezolid [#]	No	Death
Khorshidi et al, ^[36]	Female	73	Diabetic mellitus and metastatic carcinoma	<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscesses	NA	No	NA
Zhu et al, ^[64]	Male	52	No	<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscesses	Amikacin and ceftriaxone [#]	Craniotomy	Complete recovery
Sartoretti et al, ^[51]	NA	76	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and alcohol abuse	<i>Nocardia Farcinica</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscesses	Imipenem, TMP-SMX, and Meropenem [#]	Drainage	Death
Hauser et al, ^[28]	Female	54	diabetic mellitus and chronic kidney disease	<i>Nocardia nova</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscesses	Imipenem and TMP/SMX*	Yes	Recovery
Freiberg et al, ^[24]	Male	49	Renal transplantation	<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i>	16S rRNA	Spinal abscesses	imipenem, TMP/SMX, and linezolid [#]	No	Recovery
Ibrahim et al, ^[30]	Male	72	Allogeneic stem cell transplant and blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm	NA	No	Brain abscesses	TMP-SMX*	No	Recovery
Uneda et al, ^[60]	Male	65	Autoimmune hemolytic anemia	<i>Nocardia asiatica</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscesses	TMP-SMX [#]	Craniotomy	Recovery
Carrasco et al, ^[17]	Male	49	No	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Brain abscesses	amoxicillin/clavulanic acid and minocycline*	Craniotomy	Recovery
Gupta et al, ^[27]	Male	42	Diabetic mellitus, chronic kidney disease and renal transplantation	NA	No	Brain abscesses	TMP-SMX, meropenem and linezolid*	No	Recovery
Sun et al, ^[57]	Female	73	Rheumatoid arthritis, breast cancer, and diabetic mellitus	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Brain abscesses	TMP-SMX and moxifloxacin [#]	Yes	Recovery
Patel et al, ^[48]	Female	54	Hepatic cirrhosis	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Brain abscesses	Meropenem and ciprofloxacin [#]	No	Recovery
Atemnkeng et al, ^[16]	Male	63	Diabetic mellitus	<i>Nocardia asteroides</i>	No	Brain abscesses	linezolid and TMP/SMX [#]	No	Recovery
Schiaroli et al, ^[12]	Male	54	Pneumonia	<i>Nocardia paucivorans</i>	DNA sequencing	Brain abscesses	Ceftriaxone, TMP/SMX, vancomycin and rifampin*	Drainage	Recovery
Aljuboori et al, ^[14]	Male	49	Nocardial brain abscess	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Spinal abscesses	linezolid, amikacin and ciprofloxacin [#]	Laminectomy	Recovery
Yu et al, ^[62]	Male	65	No	<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i>	No	Disseminated infection	TMP/SMX, linezolid, and meropenem*	Drainage	Recovery
Lee et al, ^[38]	Male	64	Colon cancer	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	16S rRNA	Disseminated infection	TMP/SMX and imipenem [#]	Drainage	Recovery
Khadka et al, ^[35]	NA	66	Renal transplant and	NA	No	Disseminated	TMP/SMX*	Craniotomy	Recovery

			pulmonary tuberculosis			infection				
Marques et al, ^[42]	Male	78	alcohol abuse	NA	No	Disseminated infection	TMP/SMX, amikacin, and imipenem*	No		Recovery
Aguirre et al, ^[13]	Male	71	Granulomatosis with polyangiitis	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Brain abscesses and endogenous endophthalmitis	TMP/SMX and imipenem*	No		Recovery
Trehan et al, ^[59]	Male	35	Membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis	NA	No	Brain abscesses and endogenous endophthalmitis	TMP/SMX, amikacin and imipenem*	Drainage		Recovery with light perception disability
Majeed et al, ^[41]	Male	72	Mantle cell lymphoma	<i>Nocardia kroppenstedtii sp nov</i>	16S rRNA	brain abscesses and endocarditis	Meropenem, TMP/SMX, ceftriaxone, minocycline, and ciprofloxacin#	No		Death
Zhou et al, ^[63]	Male	50	Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	mNGS	Brain abscess	Meropenem and TMP/SMX*	No		Recovery
Senard et al, ^[52]	Male	12	No	<i>Nocardia elegans/aobensis/africana complex</i>	No	Brain abscess	Imipenem and ciprofloxacin*	Drainage		Death
Solano-Varela et al, ^[55]	Male	58	No	<i>Nocardia beijingensis</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscess	Meropenem, amikacin, TMP-SMX*	No		Death
Kweh et al, ^[37]	Male	60	Cardiac transplant	<i>Nocardia Nova</i>	No	Brain abscess	Meropenem and TMP/SMX*	No		Recovery
Srivastava et al, ^[56]	Male	53	No	<i>Nocardia asiatica</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscess	TMP/SMX*	No		Recovery
Yamamoto et al, ^[61]	Male	73	Pneumonia and meningitis	<i>Nocardia araoensis</i>	16S rRNA	Meningitis, ventriculitis and brain abscess	vancomycin, ceftriaxone and piperacillin*	No		Death
Tanaka et al, ^[58]	Male	68	No	<i>Nocardia beijingensis</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscess	TMP/SMX#	No		Recovery
Pan et al, ^[46]	Male	72	No	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	mNGS	Brain abscess	TMP/SMX, linezolid, and meropenem*	No		Death
Jeong et al, ^[31]	Male	51	Systemic lupus erythematosus	<i>Nocardia asiatica</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscess	TMP/SMX and ceftriaxone*	No		Death
Einstein et al, ^[22]	Male	46	Diabetic mellitus	<i>Nocardia otitidiscaviarum</i>	No	Brain abscess	amikacin, TMP/SMX, and minocycline#	Craniotomy and drainage		Recovery
Matin et al, ^[43]	Female	68	Multiple myeloma	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Brain abscess	TMP-SMX, linezolid, imipenem, and tedizolid#	Drainage		Recovery
Farran et al, ^[23]	Male	60	No	<i>Nocardia abscessus</i>	16s rRNA	Infectious intracranial aneurysm and brain abscess	Ceftriaxone and TMP/SMX*	Drainage and resection of the infected aneurysm		Recovery
Joshua et al, ^[32]	Male	73	Diabetic mellitus and autoimmune hemolytic anemia	<i>Nocardia araoensis</i>	No	Brain abscess	Meropenem and TMP/SMX*	Craniotomy		Recovery
Keenan et al, ^[34]	Male	50	HIV infection and alcohol abuse	<i>Nocardia beijingensis</i>	No	Brain abscess	Meropenem and TMP-SMX#	Craniotomy		Recovery

Pascual-Gallego et al, [47]	Male	62	No	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	16s rRNA	Brain abscess	vancomycin, imipenem, and ciprofloxacin*	Craniotomy	Recovery
Moniuszko-Malinowska et al, [44]	NA	52	No	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	16s rRNA	Chronic meningitis	TMP/SMX*	No	Full recovery
Grond et al, [26]	Male	51	Alcohol abuse	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Brain abscess	TMP/SMX*	Craniotomy	Recovery
Chaudhari et al, [18]	Male	75	Diabetic mellitus	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Brain abscess	ceftriaxone sodium, TMP-SMX, and linezolid*	Craniotomy and drainage	Recovery
Galacho-Harriero et al, [25]	Male	51	Diabetic mellitus	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	16s rRNA	Brain abscess	Linezolid, amikacin, ciprofloxacin, and TMP/SMX*	Craniotomy	Recovery
Galacho-Harriero et al, [25]	Female	68	Wegener disease	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	16s rRNA	Brain abscess	Meropenem and vancomycin#	Craniotomy	Recovery
Galacho-Harriero et al, [25]	Male	84	Asthma	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	16s rRNA	Brain abscess	Ceftriaxone and ciprofloxacin#	Craniotomy	Recovery
Livingston et al, [39]	Male	67	Metastatic prostatic cancer	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Brain abscess	meropenem, TMP/SMX, amikacin, and moxifloxacin#	Drainage	Recovery
Nasri et al, [45]	Male	91	Astrocytoma	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	16s rRNA	Meningitis	Imipenem, TMP/SMX, and Ceftriaxone*	No	Death
Tajima et al, [11]	Male	66	B-cell lymphoma	<i>Nocardia otitidiscaviarum</i>	16s rRNA	Meningitis	TMP/SMX*	No	Recovery
Shimizu et al, [54]	Female	52	Diabetic mellitus	<i>Nocardia paucivorans</i>	DNA sequencing	Brain abscess	TMP/SMX and ceftriaxone#	Craniotomy	Recovery
Effendi et al, [21]	Female	44	Autoimmune hemolytic anemia, and leukemia	<i>Nocardia thailandica</i>	16S rRNA	Brain abscess	Ceftriaxone#	Craniotomy	Recovery
Karan et al, [33]	Male	70	No	<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i>	No	Brain abscess	TMP/SMX and ceftriaxone*	Craniotomy	Recovery
Ma et al, [40]	Male	50	Diabetic mellitus	<i>Nocardia farcinica</i>	No	Spinal abscess	TMP/SMX and levofloxacin*	Laminectomy and drainage	Recovery
Huang et al, [29]	Female	61	Breast cancer and diabetic mellitus	<i>Nocardia asiatica</i>	mNGS	Brain abscess	linezolid and TMP/SMX*	Craniotomy	Recovery
AlMogbel et al, [15]	Female	65	Chronic kidney disease and idiopathic thrombocytopenia	<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i>	16s rRNA	Brain abscess	vancomycin and ceftriaxone*	Craniotomy	Recovery
Eren et al, [10]	Female	69	No	<i>Nocardia otitidiscaviarum</i>	16s rRNA	Brain abscess	meropenem and TMP/SMX*	Craniotomy	Recovery
Delavari et al, [19]	Male	50	Alcohol abuse	<i>Nocardia paucivorans</i>	16s rRNA	Brain abscess	Imipenem, moxifloxacin, and TMP/SMX*	Craniotomy	Recovery
Dioia et al, [20]	Male	58	No	<i>Nocardia beijingensis</i>	No	Brain abscess	TMP/SMX, ceftriaxone, and azithromycin#	Craniotomy	Death
Sherbuk et al, [53]	Male	40	HIV infection	<i>Nocardia abscessus</i>	16s rRNA	Disseminated infection	Ceftriaxone, doxycycline, and TMP/SMX#	No	Recovery

HIV = human immunodeficiency virus, mNGS = metagenomic next- generation sequencing, TMP-SMX = trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, NA = not available

* Empiric treatment

Targeted treatment